

SOLVING THE PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEMS OF MODERN EDUCATION BASED ON THE CULTURAL APPROACH

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Abstract. This article talks about the problems of improving the quality of education today, ideas and considerations for their elimination and defining the future, including the problems of improving educational programs, designing educational activities, and training pedagogues.

Keywords: culture, thought, socio-scientific, pedagogic, scientific-cultural, spiritual-ethical, education, technology.

РЕШЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ПРОБЛЕМ СОВРЕМЕННОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ НА ОСНОВЕ КУЛЬТУРНОГО ПОДХОДА

Аннотация. В статье говорится о проблемах повышения качества образования сегодня, идеях и соображениях по их устранению и определению будущего, в том числе о проблемах совершенствования образовательных программ, проектирования образовательной деятельности, подготовки педагогов.

Ключевые слова: культура, мысль, общественно-научная, педагогическая, научно-культурная, духовно-этическая, образование, технология.

Introduction: First of all, we need to understand the main meaning of the article. What is modern education? Does it have any benefit or harm to us? To what extent should we acquire it? Do we need pedagogy itself or have we developed pedagogical skills? By fully answering these questions, we can fully cover our topic today. This topic is one of the most relevant topics today. Where can we find qualified educators? Or where can we show the institutions that prepare for pedagogy? Of course, we can cite kindergarten, school and higher education as a clear example. Kindergarten is an educational institution that educates children up to school age and forms the first life skills. In the school, the children conduct lessons under the guidance of the teacher, and the basic preparation for life begins in this school. We said that children are educated in the kindergarten, and in the school, together with education, educational work is the main place. That is why a school is an educational institution where the young generation is informed and educated under the guidance of a teacher. In higher education institutions, future professionals learn ways to independently and creatively apply theoretical knowledge relevant to their profession during the process of professional practice. They acquire professional skills, observe and analyze the development of children, and while assessing the level of knowledge, they learn to organize

various activities for children, plan educational and educational work. All these constitute the modern education system.

We got some insights about the education system. As the education system improves, so do its problems. Earlier we used to say that the main problem in education is lack of books. Our state has provided all students with science and other books, but has this solved the problem? No. The reason for our country's lagging behind other countries was found to be the lack of modern educational programs and insufficient equipment in classrooms. And every school, especially higher education institutions, was provided with equipment based on modern, foreign education system, but were we able to fully solve the pedagogical problems with this? Of course not. During the last research, it was found that all the problem lies with the pedagogues themselves, and the pedagogues were sent to improve their qualifications abroad, and requirements were set to have various certificates and categories to get a job. But even with this, we could not make every child equally interested in reading. Even with this, we could not solve the problem. So, what other problems can we bring. Maybe all the problem is in the educational institutions themselves.

School environment.

The lack of scientific environment in schools leads to a shortage of qualified personnel and an abundance of unqualified personnel. In schools, teachers have stopped working on themselves. A large number of talented people either drop out of school or their talents remain undiscovered. Effective criteria for evaluating the quality of a teacher's lesson have not been created in our current educational system. Teachers are entangled with organizational issues. No matter how ugly it sounds, we have to admit: the lesson has become a secondary thing.

Another glaring problem is bureaucracy. Look at the form, not the content. Pedicures, posters, visual aids. The list can be continued. It is no secret that in some cases (not always) commission members try to gain reputation by reprimanding everyone wherever they go. The goal remains to punish the guilty, not to eliminate the deficiency. Sometimes there are completely illogical statements.

When we talk about the poor quality of education, for some reason we point to all the paperwork and paperwork, and the involvement of teachers in useless organizational work as the main culprits.

Is it really so? If the pedagogical load is eliminated and events are not carried out, will everything be traced? No. I do not think so. Poor education has much deeper roots. Where is the root of the problem itself?

Children are forced to go to school and college. The goal of students to go to university is only to get a diploma. If possible, he does not go to study at all, but takes grades. Students have no interest in learning. In some cases, the interest decreases as they move to a higher class. The main reason for this is why students are paying attention to their environment and education. I found the reason for this to be in modern technologies. We have brought modern technologies to improve the quality of development and education, but the extent to which they are used is left up to the students themselves. A question that always bothers me is why do parents hand their young children a phone to comfort them? Why is the latest phone in the hands of a second- and third-grader? Why are we giving school children computers instead of books? Why, why are we silently watching the young generation standing on the edge of the cliff. We always blame the teachers,

the educational programs, but we don't blame the children? In ancient times, when it was difficult to study and get education, our forefathers studied, studied and searched. He even memorized the Koranic books. Mind you, this is not an easy task. But how did they do these things, how did they reach this level, when there were no teachers to teach, enough books, conditions? Of course, there were no phones stealing all of our time along with the things we counted at that time. We do not even notice that these phones, which are said to serve good, work only and only to our detriment. Various mobile games that have occupied the minds and bodies of teenage children are destroying their psychology. Once the child loses the game, he plays again and again until he wins. He gets so involved in the game that he does not hear any words around him. His imagination is occupied only with games and robots, which makes him lose interest in life. After all, how can we say that a child who has no interest in life will grow into a mature and knowledgeable scientist. How can children who kill people in phone games respect their teachers and parents. Can we attract a child who no one respects, who has no interest in studying? Of course not.

Your parents are the cause of all these situations. They have no respect for education. Therefore, there is no effort to improve the quality of work, that is, to attract the best personnel. By themselves, parents do not want their child to be educated and have a high level. This is the biggest problem in education. If the population had a high need for education, they would seek knowledge. They would appreciate knowledgeable teachers. They were interested in learning, not grades. They demanded a good lesson from the teacher and were ready to pay accordingly.

The only way to overcome these problems is for everyone to work together. The teacher is required to:

1. To interest students;
2. Giving the right direction;
3. Education of thought;
4. Motivation.

Parents are required to always be attentive to their children, monitor their reading and behavior, and if possible, give them various books as gifts. Deal with your child as a friend, not as an official person, and solve problems and shortcomings together. Finally, the demand from the younger generation is not to waste time on education, to respect everyone who is older than them. If we work together like this, hand in hand, we can easily solve all these problems.

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